

**ORGANIZING START-UP PROJECTS ABOUT CARDIO VESSELS AND
USING THEM IN PRACTICE**

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Abstract. In this article presents about the role of Uzbek women and girls' participation in education and global society. To sum up, a lot of work is being done to ensure gender equality, to ensure the full participation of women in the implementation of political, social and economic tasks that are the basis of the stability of the state and society.

Key words: activity of women, Tumaris.Tech program, Youth Support, Women Visage Foundation.

Tumaris.Tech is one of the largest projects implemented by IT Park Uzbekistan in cooperation with the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). It was launched in July 2020. The Tumaris.Tech program fully supports women's business initiatives. The project consists of several components. It aims to increase the involvement of women in the ICT ecosystem, and includes areas ranging from BPO (Business Process Outsourcing) development to education for women aspiring freelancers, startup development, and investment training. In two years, the project has borne fruit in the form of 30 startups and more than 200 girls have had the opportunity to get an IT education. Currently, the project is expanding throughout Central Asia, and now representatives of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan and Tajikistan can participate in Tumaris.Tech programs. I am as listener and as winner this Tumaris.Tech start up center gaining more knowledge and skills. I am participating with my start up project “Cardio Vessel” and this project about creating a two-phase model based on hemodynamic laws in the calculation of blood velocity in thrombi and plaques in cardiovascular diseases and the expression of blood through filtration problems. The incubation program is an educational and practical program, within which the idea of a startup project is formed and developed, in other words, it is a program for enthusiasts who have an idea, but no business plan, no clear understanding of how this can be implemented at all (from idea to MVP).

Visage Women Foundation is an NGO (Non-Governmental Organization) without affiliation to any Governmental Agencies directly or indirectly. As volunteer and

speaker this organization I found my role for my future. Olamide Akintola coaches women, provides strategies and solutions, motivates and helps women who want to do better for themselves. She is a mother, a minister of the gospel, an education consultant, a writer, a journalist and a business woman.

She is the publisher of Visage Magazine, a magazine that features inspiring and motivating articles for women with seasoned writers. Her passion for women and girls brought about the birth of Visage Women Foundation which has since inception touch lives in various capacity and shun some evil vices in our society. Her regular talk show for teenage girls tagged 'Girls Day Out' has transformed many lives.

I will invest and exchange my experience in technical innovations in healthcare and hospitals/ startup strategies of projects and entrepreneurship skills and use my passion for innovative solutions to bring more value to the mentorship. Our young team gives new ideas and scientific solving problems had departments of the local conference. My research topic about "Creation of a mathematical model and software for the pathology of the circulatory system in the cardiovascular system". As a result, participating in meeting Tech Rech project I achieved more than what I dreamed about it. All the dissertations and scientists that they considered studied the creation of a mathematical model of blood circulation and what problems were raised. The relevance of the topic is sometimes that, from different pathologies, doctors can not put the diagnosis of the heart in circulation. Blood circulation is a unique system that has blood transport that runs there. In different pathologies, the heart and blood circulation give different results.

The implementation of this project includes the following tasks:

1. Analyzing of the results of a healthy person and the general type of all cardiovascular diseases in a narrow area and the study of the effect of covid 19 virus on the cardiovascular system.
2. Analyzing all mathematical models and consult with cardiologists on how to treat other diseases arising in the new era.
3. Developing a mobile cardiology application with the necessary tools for software and PC.

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